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ABSTRACTS

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A Simulation-Based Approach for Optimizing Microfluidic Systems for Point-of-Care Diagnostics

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Abstract: In the face of global health challenges, particularly in rural and semi-rural areas, the demand for accessible and affordable healthcare remains crucial. This study explores the application of microfluidic technology, utilizing COMSOL Multiphysics software to simulate blood flow within a polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS)-based conduit. The simulations investigate various physical configurations, including capillary action and pressure-gradient environments, to understand the dynamics of blood flow in restricted spaces. The goal is to contribute to the development of Point-of-Care diagnostic tools, addressing the healthcare needs of underserved populations worldwide. The findings reveal limitations in relying solely on capillary effects for blood displacement and emphasize the necessity of a pressure gradient. The study also explores the impact of channel width and geometry on blood flow, with bent geometries showing better performance. Additionally, the particle tracing model highlights the importance of optimizing micro-reservoir shapes for efficient erythrocyte movement. While the study demonstrates the potential for blood flow and cell counting in the given channels, it emphasizes the need for further simulations to refine and establish a reliable model for enhanced Point-of-Care diagnostics.

Keywords: Blood flow simulation, capillary action, COMSOL Multiphysics simulation, microfluidic systems, particle tracing model, point-of-care diagnostic devices, pressure driven flow.

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